

The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Swansea

Expert source: Thomas Alexander Husøy, Swansea University

Entered by Thomas Alexander Husøy, Swansea University

** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

Entry tags: English, Religious Group, Lutheran Church, Lutheranism, Language, Protestantism, Religious Place

The Norwegian Church in Swansea was a Norwegian Seamen's Mission Church in the port city of Swansea in Wales, United Kingdom. Mission activity began in Swansea already in 1866, when the Norwegian Seamen's Mission began their activity in the neighbouring city of Cardiff. Yet, in 1907 a decision was made to build a new church in Swansea. The building that was erected in Swansea was originally standing in Newport, and was a substation of the church in Cardiff. The Seamen's Mission remained active in Swansea until 1964, when they left the city. The church did remain in use by the Norwegian diaspora and the Lutheran community in city until 1998.

Date Range: 1907 CE - 1998 CE

Region: The Norwegian Church in Swansea

Region tags: United Kingdom

The current location of the former Norwegian Seamen's Church near the Prince of Wales dock in Cardiff. The building is now Appletree Nursery, but remains an important part of the diasporic cultural heritage in the city.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Williams, David . Mymryn o Norwy Yng Nghymru: Atgofion Am Yr Eglwysi Morwyr Norwyaid/A Little Piece of Norway in Wales: Recollections of the Norwegian Seamen's Churches/En Lite Stykke Norge i Wales: Minner Fra de Norske Sjømannskirkene. Edited by Karen Allen and Wenche Davies. Cardiff: Norwegian Church Cultural Centre, 2006.
- Source 2: Aarseth, Ivar, and Christian Bruun. Den Norske Sjomandsmission i Bristolkanalens Havne, 1866-1916. Cardiff: South Wales Printing and Publishing Company, 1916.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://archwilio.org.uk/her/chi3/arch.php?county=Glamorgan%20Gwent%20Archaeological%20Trust=&lang=eng>
- Source 1 Description: Archwilio record for the Norwegian Church i Swansea
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.sjomannskirken.no/historien-til/swansea/>
- Source 2 Description: Norwegian Seamen's Mission history page about the church in Swansea
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.jlb2011.co.uk/walespic/churches/swansea7.htm>
- Source 3 Description: General information about the Norwegian Church in Swansea

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: Not a natural landscape feature, but featured as a part of the industrial landscape of the city during the early and mid-19th century.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The church was located in the industrial port area of the city, and originally stood approximately 300 meters from where it is now. It was moved to its current location as a part of Swansea's ambitious SA1 redevelopments.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: The structure is shaped as a traditional Norwegian village chapel.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: The church would originally have had a model of a ship in the roof, as a reference to the seafaring history of Norway and the mission's connection to the city.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: It is a part of the historical landscape of Swansea's docklands, where for a period most of the world's copper was exported. Earning the city its nickname Copperopolis.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Social

Notes: Norwegian Seamen's Churches contained a reading room and social space used for Norwegians and Scandinavians abroad.

– Political

Notes: Norwegian Churches was also a political space, emphasising Norwegian national identity and nationalism among sailors, especially in the years following the dissolution of the union between Norway and Sweden in 1905.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: But like the church in Cardiff it was built in corrugated iron to make it easy to moved if needed. The church in Swansea was in fact moved to this city in 1910, from Newport near the English border.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, both when it first moved to Swansea in 1910 and then when it was moved again as a part of the SA1 developments in Swansea.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: But it has been dismantled and moved twice thus far.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Especially when it was moved from Newport to Swansea, and secondly, when the building was moved within Swansea in the early 2000s.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Christian god.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: Not a political entity, but it was commissioned and built by the Norwegian Seamen's Mission with support from the Church of Norway.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Men

– Women

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: The church was built by the Norwegian community in the city and sailors from Norway.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The event her refers to the sharp increase of Norwegian sailors in Swansea in the late 19th and early 20th century, especially relating to the copper industry.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳

Earth

– No

↳

Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: wooden planks/beams, corrugated iron, concrete.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: When the building was operational as a church it had a model of ship in the roof, a harmonium, as well as a statues and other minor decorating features around the building.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Figures showing Jesus was once in the church.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: Although the decoration that used to be in the church can no longer be seen in the Church in Cardiff, they can still be seen the Seamen's Churches archive and museum in Bergen (access by appointment).

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Notes: They were stained glass windows.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– I don't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: N/A

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian god is often depicted as anthropomorphic.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Although arguably, also through the prayers of Norwegian sailors

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Communication with god can be achieved through prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: This would vary depending on the number of sailors in the port and type of event.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Rituals would take place depending on when needed in relations to events like weddings and funerals. Other rituals such as sermons would take place at least once a week and confirmations a few times a year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Although most of the users of the church were seafarer's from Norway arriving in Wales, not as a part of pilgrimage but as a part of the global Norwegian trade in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Religious and social gatherings at the church was sometimes followed by a feast and party within the local Norwegian community in Swansea.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– No

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Within the reading room of the church.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: All the typical Christian festivals; Easter, Christmas etc. as well as Norwegian cultural festivals, such as the annual celebration of the constitution day.

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: It is impossible to say with certainty, as it would change depending on the number of Norwegian sailors within port of Swansea at any given time.

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Religious professionals

Notes: No limits, the full congregation could take part in food consumption.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

- Yes

- ↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Whilst women could have influential roles within the Norwegian Seamen's Mission, they could originally not hold the role of pastor. This have now changed and in the contemporary world , and there now female pastors within the Norwegian Seamen's world.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: They were Norwegians appointed by the mission's main office in Bergen, and often came from a Norwegian professional or educational background, and was of Norwegian ethnic origin.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Norwegian Seamen's pastors would often serve for a period of time, before moving onto the next seamen's church or taking up office at another church in Norway.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Although the pastor would have his own residence within the city.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:
– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– No

↳ Function for water management:
– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The church provided various services for the local community, as an example, in addition to being a place of religious worship it was also a place for social gatherings and during World War II it even functioned as a bank, lending money to sailors who visited the church.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Norwegian Seamen's Mission churches had a library within it, hosting a collection of Norwegian books and newspapers. These were circulated between various Seamen's Churches, new books were brought in by ship and old books were taken out, ensuring that a variety of books were present in the churches. This allowed sailors to stay on top of current affairs back in Norway and current Norwegian literature.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Swansea, Aarseth, Ivar, and Christian Bruun. *Den Norske Sjømandmission I Bristolkanalens Havne.*, Cardiff: South Wales Printing and Publishing Company, 1916.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Swansea, Williams, Erin. "Swansea's Norwegian Church". *Welsh Norwegian Society Magazine*, 2020.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Swansea, Sivertsen, W. *Memoirs of Captain W J Sivertsen of Christiansand (norway) and Swansea, Founder of the Norwegian Church in Swansea*. Swansea: West Glamorgan Archive Service, 1931.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Swansea, Husøy, Thomas Alexander. "The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff Bay". *The Database of Religious History*, 2023.